

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF USING ART THERAPY IN PSYCHOCORRECTIONAL WORK WITH CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15852299>

Abstract: This article discusses modern forms and methods of art therapy in psychocorrectional work with children with autism spectrum disorders. In particular, the theoretical foundations and practical application of such methods as art therapy, isotherapy, bibliotherapy, sand therapy, play therapy, hippotherapy, garden therapy and animation therapy are considered. The methods presented in the article are significant in that they are aimed at stabilizing the emotional state of children, increasing the level of socialization, and developing fine motor skills and speech functions. Also, ways to increase the effectiveness of correctional work by ensuring parental participation are analyzed.

Keywords: autism, psychocorrection, art therapy, isotherapy, bibliotherapy, sand therapy, play therapy, garden therapy, hippotherapy, animation therapy, emotional development, social adaptation

Introduction. In the field of special pedagogy, a complete theoretical and practical approach to the correction of childhood autism has been developed (K.S. Lebedinskaya, O.S. Nikol'skaya, 1991; O.S. Nikol'skaya, E.R. Bayenskaya, M.M. Liebling, 1997). The basis of the system of psychological correctional assistance to a child with autism and his family members is based on the idea of a primary violation of the development of the affective sphere in the general structure of the syndrome (O.S. Nikol'skaya, 1985, 1999). Correctional work with children with ASD is carried out on the basis of the approach (method) of K.S. Lebedinskaya.

Thus, there are many methods of correcting autism in the world: holding therapy, music therapy, water therapy, play classes, therapy with dolphins, trampoline therapy, hitting a wet cloth, etc. The following are especially widely used in practice:

- correction-treatment through art (art therapy),
- correction-treatment through books (bibliotherapy),
- correction-treatment through games,
- correction-treatment through clay,
- music therapy,
- fairy tale therapy,
- correction-treatment through plants (garden therapy),
- correction-treatment through horseback riding (hippotherapy),
- computer technologies,
- animation therapy,
- correction-treatment through travel (turotherapy),
- sand therapy, etc.

By correction-treatment through art (art therapy) is meant a set of methods that use artistic activities (painting, dance, music, poetry, theater, artistic reading, rhetoric) aimed at eliminating or compensating for a deficiency.

In rehabilitation practice, types of art therapy are selected depending on the type and nature of the defect, as well as the specific nature of the impact on this or that defect. For example, music and visual arts help children with disabilities develop the ability to correctly perceive space and time in the surrounding world, while theater, rhetoric and dance help such children coordinate their behavior, thereby forming in them the skills of acceptable behavior in communicating with others. Reading is an important means of developing intellectual abilities in children with all types of disabilities, but for children with vision and hearing problems it is the most effective way to expand contacts with the socio-cultural environment.

Art therapy makes particularly extensive use of the possibilities of fine arts (isotherapy): isotherapy makes up a large part of art therapy. The main goal of isotherapy is to activate (or compensate for) the positive psychic potential of a child with developmental disabilities through creative visual activity.

It is not necessary to have special artistic abilities for isotherapy. The main thing is that a child with disabilities should be able to express his inner state and feelings through drawing. The process of drawing is directly related to important mental functions such as visual perception, motor coordination, speech, and thinking, and not only helps the development of speech function, but also connects these functions, thereby helping the child to organize and form his own ideas about the world around him.

Correction-treatment through books (bibliotherapy) is carried out more in the direction of social, cultural-educational, psychological rehabilitation. It is carried out through literary reading, discussion, literary evenings, meetings with the heroes and authors of works, book exhibitions, etc.

- Correction-treatment through games (game therapy) is a technology consisting of a set of rehabilitation game methods, forms, means, situations. Game therapy performs many important functions. These are: socialization, development, upbringing, education, adaptation, relaxation and correction.

The game helps to activate a child with autism, enriches the experience of interpersonal communication and communication, teaches to master the forms of interaction individually and in a group.

- Fairy tale therapy is one of the leading types and methods of emotional-psychological, pedagogical influence on the personality of a child with developmental disabilities and its socio-moral formation.

- In clay correction-treatment, work is carried out mainly with clay, plasticine, dough and similar elastic materials. This method of work combines medical, valeological, culturally oriented and creative elements.

Another technology used in correctional-developmental classes with preschool children with autism is sand therapy (sand treatment), in which a child (sometimes an adult) creates his own separate world from sand and small figures. This method has its own ancient and interesting history and has retained its place in scientific-theoretical and technical progress at present and in the future.

- Sand is a material with its own special properties. When we cover our hands with dry sand (sand), we feel a special sense of calm; By scattering sand with our hands, moving it from one place to another, we create various shapes, wind and sand together create the image of a desert. When sand mixes with water, it darkens and becomes solid, taking on the appearance

of the earth. In this case, it is possible to create various shapes with sand (landscapes, multi-story buildings, various objects). Based on such an activity, the child creates his own world in his imagination and temporarily lives in it. The child cannot explain his difficulties in words like adults, but he can describe this situation through sand drawings. The development of tactile perception and fine motor skills is an additional positive effect for autistic children. In the process of work, the child mixes sand with water, if necessary, and makes mountains, houses, landscapes. The child also makes various miniature figures in the process of work: people, animals, trees, buildings, etc. Making various figures and objects in this way is important for the child to create his own world.

Speech therapy sessions with children with autism using sand therapy are conducted individually in specially organized playrooms. Toys are specially selected for sand therapy: dollhouses, various dolls, cars, tables for sand and water, toy animals, constructors, etc. The game is conducted under the supervision of a speech therapist, without disturbing the child. During the game, the problems and causes of the child with autism are identified and the child is helped to eliminate them. The speech therapist often involves parents in the game in order to improve the relationship between the child and the parents.

- Correction-treatment with the help of plants (garden therapy) is a separate direction of psychosocial rehabilitation of children with disabilities, this method of work is carried out by working with plants and caring for them.

- Correction-treatment on horseback (hippotherapy). This method involves the rehabilitation and improvement of children with disabilities by riding horses. Hippotherapy helps to improve the overall health of the child's body, has a psychological, aesthetic, and educational effect on him.

Animation therapy is one of the socio-psychological methods of correctional and therapeutic work, which, using art and cultural institutions, helps a child with developmental disabilities to adapt to the socio-cultural environment, intellectual development, and integration into the everyday socio-cultural environment.

Conclusion. Art-based therapy methods are important in adapting children with autism to the socio-cultural environment and supporting their psychological development. These methods are selected based on the individual needs of the child and serve to form emotional stability, communication skills, motor skills and social relationships. Therefore, a comprehensive approach based on art therapy is one of the effective directions in psychocorrectional work with children with autism.

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